

Experimental Evaluation of an Explicit Model Predictive Controller for an Adhesion Vortex Actuated Climbing Robot

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Abstract—This article establishes an Explicit Model Predictive Control (EMPC) scheme for controlling the adhesion of a climbing Vortex Robot (VR). The VR utilizes an Electric Ducted Fan (EDF) as the Vortex Actuator (VA), where the dynamics have been identified via an Autoregressive-Moving-Average with eXternal input (ARMAX) identification scheme. An explicit controller via the use of a Constraint Finite Time Optimal Control (CFTOC) approach is designed in an offline manner and implemented for the case of the VR, where the adhesion reference is provided by a static force model. The presented approach results in a lookup table realization that ensures overall system stability in all state transitions, while being able to accurately control the adhesion force for arbitrary setup orientations. The efficacy of the proposed control scheme is demonstrated through experimental results involving a moving test surface under random inclinations and robot orientations.

I. INTRODUCTION

There is a growing need for robotic setups that carry out inspection tasks of large-scale infrastructure in an autonomous manner. Maintenance tasks, such as thickness measurement, visual surveillance, coating, brushing, etc. are few examples of inspection and repair applications that are increasingly being performed by robotic platforms. In general, the aging and remote infrastructure, that it is difficult or dangerous to be reached by human inspectors, could be accessed by inspection robots that are operating in autonomous or semi-autonomous modes. In this application area, climbing robots are an increasing trend for their capability to access difficult and dangerous to reach areas while being equipped with tools and sensors, as it is highlighted in the following indicative work [1]–[6].

Towards this direction, a novel climbing Vortex Robotic Platform (VRP) [7] has been proposed to perform inspection and repair on airplane fuselages with the goal of having a modular sensorial system. The adhesion technology selected for this robot, hereafter referred to as vortex actuation [8], utilizes an Electric Ducted Fan (EDF) to maintain adhesion on the various inclination and curved surfaces of the airplane, without requiring contact with the surface. The vast majority of climbing robots, independently of the adhesion method (magnetic, pneumatic, gripping etc), rely on an on-off adhesion, without being able to effectively control the level of adhesion. Only a few attempts found in the related

literature, have addressed the issue of controlled adhesion for wall climbing robots [9], [10], thus highlighting the need for advanced control schemes in order to minimize power consumption while satisfying all demanding operation requirements. In an effort to address this research gap, this work aims to design and experimentally evaluate an Explicit Model Predictive Control (EMPC), in the form of a Constraint Finite Time Optimal (CFTO)-controller for the Vortex Actuator (VA). The control goal is to regulate the level of adhesion via a model-based static force model for reserving power resources and thus minimizing the overall cost of deployment and operation.

The utilized discrete Model Predictive Control (MPC) scheme is an optimal control strategy that has been quite popular in the process industry [11] over the last decades, while in recent years there has been a shift for the adoption of this powerful control scheme in the area of Robotics [12]–[14]. The MPC considers the future outputs of the system and while handling input-output and state constraints, solves an online optimization problem [15]. The optimization process is repeated at every iteration and the complexity of this calculation depends on various characteristics, such as the complexity of the model, the prediction and control horizon, the number of optimization variables, constraints etc. This repeated task is considered to be computational intensive [16] and quite often there is a need for expensive computation units to handle these types of problems. A solution to this computational burden is the use of an EMPC. The EMPC pre-calculates the optimal control solution and provides the feedback law as a piecewise affine function, while the overall control structure is being provided in the form of a look-up table.

The novelty of this article stems from the design of an EMPC to regulate the adhesion level of a Vortex Robot (VR). The explicit controller is implemented via the Multi-Parametric Toolbox (MPT) [17] and is applied on the case of a model-based static force computation of the required adhesion for given robot orientation. The overall control scheme is being experimentally evaluated to demonstrate its applicability and efficiency in regulating the adhesion regardless of test surface orientation changes. The generated adhesion force from the EDF is a multivariable problem, where the size of the EDF shroud, the distance, the inclination and curvature of the test surface play a crucial role on the performance of the VA and, consequently, the VRP [8]. In addition, noisy measurements from the force sensors

This work has received funding from the European Unions H2020 Framework Programme under the call FET-OPEN, Grant Agreement No.665238 (Project CompInnova).

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and various additive disturbances make the identification procedure a challenging task. In the proposed framework, it is demonstrated the utilization of a single model to cover the complete operation region of the VA.

The rest of this article is structured as follows. In Section II the robot's design and its components are presented along with its adhesion properties. In Section III, the control formulation is provided, while the experimental results of this study are presented in Section IV. Finally, concluding remarks and future work are discussed in V.

II. ROBOTIC SETUP

The VRP presented in [7] uses an EDF-based actuator to actively adhere on surfaces of alternate inclination and different curvature. The target application of this robot is the autonomous inspection and repair tasks on composite airplane fuselages. The robot can handle different types of tools and sensors based on a modularized design, while the ability of the VA to generate negative pressure, when its ducted structure is placed at a predetermined distance from a surface [18], [8] is utilized for the generation of a high adhesion force. This generated force is not only supporting the robot for steady adhesion and secure operation but increases its permissible payload and its capability of handling heavy tools and sensors.

Fig. 1. The developed Vortex Robotic Platform (VRP) with highlighted its main components.

The VRP prototype depicted in Fig. 1 is a skid-steering robot with four wheels actuated via smart servos. The total weight of the platform is approximately 2.1 kg. The EDF is located at the center of the VR and it is supported from a ring-shaped frame, which is connected on the VR's frame with carbon fiber tubes. The connections of carbon fiber tubes end up in a casing, while at the lower part of the casing load cells have been installed, with the carbon fiber tubes placed on top of them. The load cells are utilized as force sensors and they are able to sense the vertical force component exerted from the EDF to the test surface. Thus, by enabling force measurements, the VR can operate with a controlled adhesion level, instead of an on/off technique,

which results in more efficient power consumption during operation and overall increased performance.

Fig. 2 depicts the main components of the VA, which have been used on the robot as its core actuation system to enable a successful adhesion to any surface inclination. The VA is composed of the Electronic Speed Controller (ESC) the EDF and the load cells. The ESC controls the current provided to the EDF, while the adhesion force, generated from the EDF, is measured from the load cells.

Fig. 2. Main components of the VA

The robot uses a commercially available EDF developed by Hobbyking, with a YEP-150A Electronic Speed Controller (ESC) for handling the high currents requirements for the given EDF. To sense the generated force from the EDF, two TE Connectivity FX1901 button load cells are utilized, with a PhidgetBridge 1046_0B to acquire the measured force signals.

Finally, a EA-PSI 8080-70 2U power supply was utilized for powering the VA. The acquisition of the setups sensor data and the control of the EDFs operation was achieved via a National Instruments USB-6008 card and an Arduino Mega board, while the main control and programming of the setup was performed in a ground workstation (Windows 7, 64-b, Intel i7 processor, 32-Gb RAM).

III. MODELING AND CONTROL SYNTHESIS

A. Critical Adhesion Model

Fig. 3 depicts the Degrees-of-Freedom (DoF) of the VR and the main geometrical components. For the design of the required adhesion level, the successful adhesion is considered when the robotic platform remains attached and immobilized i.e $\omega_1 = \omega_2 = \omega_3 = \omega_4 = 0$ during inclination changes of the $\{\phi, \theta, \psi\} = \{\text{roll, pitch and yaw}\}$ on the robot's frame $\{G_1\}$ with respect to the global frame $\{G\}$. For this purpose, the critical adhesion force F_c has been derived from the geometrical model [19].

$$F_c = \frac{mg}{\mu} \sqrt{(s\phi)^2 + (c\phi s\theta)^2} - mgc\phi c\theta, \quad (1)$$

where m is the mass of the system, g is the gravitational acceleration, μ is the friction coefficient and c, s the trigonometric functions \cos and \sin , respectively. From (1) it can be noticed that the critical force F_c is independent from the rotation around the z -axis. Furthermore, below some critical angles, denoted as ϕ_c, θ_c that are dependent on the friction and the mass of the platform, the described model (1) results into negative forces that are not feasible to be reached in the real-life setup. Thus, the updated model, that takes into account these critical angles, is provided by:

Fig. 3. Overview of the VR's DoF and main geometrical properties.

$$F_c = \begin{cases} 0 & 0 \leq \gamma < \gamma_c \\ \frac{mg}{\mu} \sqrt{(s\phi)^2 + (c\phi s\theta)^2} - mgc\phi c\theta & \gamma_c \leq \gamma < (2\pi - \gamma_c) \\ 0 & (2\pi - \gamma_c) \leq \gamma \leq 2\pi \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where γ is defined as $\gamma = \sqrt{\phi^2 + \theta^2}$. In addition, the load cells used for the force measurement, are able to sense the reaction force $F_S = \sum_{i=1}^2 F_{S,i}$ under the assumption that the load cells are only contact points between the EDF and the robot's frame. To translate the acquired force measurement of the load cells to adhesion force at the different plane orientations the following conversion is used,

$$F_{VA} = F_S - m'gc\phi c\theta, \quad (3)$$

where m' is the mass of the EDF and the supported components connected to the load cells. Under the assumption that the geometrical properties do not alter significantly during motion, the same critical adhesion model is used when $\omega_1 = \omega_2 = \omega_3 = \omega_4 \neq 0$.

B. Vortex Actuator Model

As mentioned in the previous section, the VA is composed of three main components, namely the ESC, the EDF and the load cells. Since this system presents nonlinearities and hysteretic phenomena, it has been modelled as a black box with the use of polynomial identification. Thus, the general Single-Input Single-Output (SISO) discrete time system can be described from an Autoregressive-Moving-Average with eXternal input (ARMAX) model as it follows [20]:

$$A(q^{-1})y(k) = B(q^{-1})u(k) + C(q^{-1})w(k) \quad (4)$$

where $y(k)$ is the output, $u(k)$ is the input, $w(k)$ is the noise and q^{-1} is the backward shift operator. Finally,

$$\begin{aligned} A(q^{-1}) &= 1 + a_1q^{-1} + \dots + a_nq^{-n} \\ B(q^{-1}) &= b_1q^{-1} + \dots + b_mq^{-m}, \\ C(q^{-1}) &= 1 + c_1q^{-1} + \dots + c_nq^{-n} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

at the k^{th} sample instant, where a vector $\theta^T = [a_1, \dots, a_{n_a}, b_0, \dots, b_{n_b}, c_1, \dots, c_{n_c}]$ contains the estimated parameters, while the regression vector $\phi(k) = [-y(k-1), \dots, -y(k-n_a), u(k), \dots, u(k-n_b)]^T$ contains the past inputs $u(\cdot)$, the outputs $y(\cdot)$, with n_a , n_b and n_c to correspond to the orders of the output, input and the disturbance term respectively.

The identified linear discrete-time state space model is defined in ((4)) as:

$$\begin{aligned} x(k+1) &= Ax(k) + Bu(k) \\ y(k) &= Cx(k) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

for $x = x_0 \in \mathbb{R}^p$ as the initial conditions, where $u(k) \in \mathbb{R}$ is the control input $x(k) \in \mathbb{R}^p$ are the states of the system and finally $y(k) \in \mathbb{R}$ is the system output. The estimated matrices A, B are expressed in their observable canonical form, while the parameters a_1, \dots, a_q and b_0, \dots, b_p are the identified parameters from the polynomial identification.

$$\begin{aligned} A &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 1 \\ -a_q & -a_{q-1} & -a_{q-2} & \dots & -a_1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad B = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \\ C &= [b_p \quad b_{p-1} \quad \dots \quad b_1]. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

C. Control Formulation

To regulate the adhesion force generated from the EDF, the following MPC problem is formulated:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{minimize} \quad & \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \left(\Delta F'_{VA,t+k|t} Q \Delta F_{VA,t+k|t} + \Delta T'_{t+k|t} R \Delta T_{t+k|t} \right) \\ \text{subject to} \quad & F_{VA,min} \leq F_{VA,k} \leq F_{VA,max}, \quad k = 1, \dots, N_p, \\ & T_{min} \leq T_k \leq T_{max}, \quad k = 1, \dots, N_p, \\ & \Delta T_{min} \leq \Delta T_k \leq \Delta T_{max}, \quad k = 1, \dots, N_p, \\ & \Delta F_{VA,t+k|t} = F_{VA,t+k|t} - F_{ref}(t), \quad k > 0, \\ & x_{k+1} = Ax_k + Bu_k, \quad k > 0, \\ & y_{k+1} = Cx_k, \quad k > 0, \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

which is solved at every time instant t , where $\Delta F'_{VA,t+k|t}$ denotes the predicted force error at time $t+k$, obtained by applying the input sequence T_t, \dots, T_{t+k-1} to (7), starting from the some initial conditions x_0 . Furthermore, Q, R are the weight matrices of the optimization problem, while the constraints for the variables of the system are denoted as $(\cdot)_{min,max}$, with $N_p, N_c \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ to denote the prediction and control horizon respectively.

The explicit controller receives as an input the reference adhesion force $F_{ref}(k)$, the feedback from the load cells $F_{VA}(k)$ and the previous input $T(k-1)$. The future control input vector $U_i(k)$ is of a size N_c and it is given from the pre-calculated EMPC and the next control action $T(k) = U_1(k)$. The measured force, from the load cells F_S is exerted from the EDF and it is filtered, based on the orientation of the robot at every iteration, to calculate the vertical component

Fig. 4. EMPC overall proposed control scheme for the adhesion regulation of the VR

of the force. The force filtering results into the F_{VA} , which indicates the adhesion level.

For a given state vector $x(k)$ the optimal solution is a PWA function of the form [15]

$$T_0(x_0) = \begin{cases} F_1 x_0 + G_1 & \text{if } x_0 \in \mathcal{R}_1 \\ \vdots \\ F_M x_0 + G_M & \text{if } x_0 \in \mathcal{R}_M \end{cases}, \quad (9)$$

where the parameter F_i and G_i are obtained from the MPT. $\mathcal{R}_i = \{x | H_i x \leq h_i\}$ are M polyhedral critical regions obtained as well from the MPT [16]. The explicit solution of the optimization problem provides a look-up table, which converts the on-line optimization problem to a on-line sequential search algorithm.

The block diagram for the proposed adhesion control scheme is presented in Fig. 4. At each iteration the robot's orientation roll ϕ and pitch θ are assumed to be known and measurable, while are fed as feedback to the system. From the geometrical model, the critical adhesion F_c is calculated from (2) by utilizing the orientation feedback, its weight, payload and estimated friction between the wheels and the target surface. The reference force $F_{ref}(k)$ is calculated with the addition of a compensator gain $K \in [1, 2]$ that accounts for the cabling load acting from the Center-of-Mass (CM) of the robot, as well as any modeling inaccuracies.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

The system identification has been performed under iterative simulation and experimental trials with the use of open-loop input-output data. The ARMAX identification has been performed for three different operating regions, where the input data T is 20–40%, 60–80%, 80–100% and the output data F_{VA} is 8–18N, 32–50N, 50–68N respectively. The orders of the identified models have been fine-tuned to be $n_a = 1$, $n_b = 3$, $n_c = 1$ and $n_d = 1$. The VA simulated response is presented based on the identified models F_{modeli} $i=(1-3)$ in Fig. 5. The F_{model3} has an adequate tracking when the input to the system is in the region $0 \leq T[\%] \leq 40$, while the F_{model1} matches better the open loop response at higher input values. The model F_{model2} results into a better tracking of the output at an input $50 \leq T[\%] \leq 70$. For the experiments of this article, a single model was used to

validate the designed controller. The F_{model2} is selected as the candidate model because of its operation at the most common operation region, based on iterative experimental trials. From the system identification process, the identified parameters are provided in a state space form (10).

Fig. 5. VA identification results at different operating points.

$$\begin{aligned} x(k+1) &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.8792 \end{bmatrix} x(k) + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} u(k) \\ y(k) &= [0.0239 \quad 0.0765 \quad -0.0230] x(k) \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

The output constraints of the controller have been set to $0 \leq F_{VA}[\text{N}] \leq 68$ while the input is constrained at the operation region of ESC $0 \leq T[\%] \leq 100$. The error ΔF_{VA} of the reference point to the measured force has been penalized by a factor $Q = 2$ and the input change has been penalized by $R = 0.01$. The discrete time model has sampling time $T_s = 25$ ms and the resulted EMPC consists of 25 regions. For the design of the explicit controller the MPT is utilized. The controller has been tuned with the MATLAB software. Finally, the resulted explicit controller is exported in C-code.

For the experimental evaluation of the controller, a rotating platform with one DoF is utilized, which is depicted in

Fig. 6. The VRP under experimental evaluation of its locomotion and adhesion properties on an inclined curved test surface.

Fig. 6a. A curved test surface of a Boeing 737 fuselage is attached on the manually rotated platform, while the VR adhesion capabilities are tested with the robotic platform immobilized on top of the target surface, $\omega_i = 0$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, 4$. For the presented experiment, the close loop performance is tested on two complete rotations (clockwise and counterclockwise). For the localization of the robot, the VICON motion capturing system has been utilized that provides the x, y, z position and the ϕ, θ, ψ orientation feedback. The static friction between the wheels and the test surface has been experimentally estimated at approximately $\mu = 0.56$.

Photographic stills from the experimental evaluation are provided in Fig. 6(b),(c) where the control scheme manages to keep the robot successfully attached on the test surface regardless of the surface orientations. In Fig. 7 the control performance of the EMPC is depicted. The generated force F_{VA} shows locally an accurate tracking of the reference force F_{ref} around an 40 – 70N operation region for which the controller has been designed. It has to be noted that the critical adhesion F_c compensator gain is tuned and set to $K = 1.3$. It has to be noted that the single model inaccuracy around the operating point of 0 – 40N requires the use of the force compensator in order for the overall scheme to provide sufficient thrust and reach the critical force levels. This can be observed clearly when the roll orientation is around $\theta = 180^\circ$, where the additive constant compensator reaches the adhesion force to a saturation point. The use

of a switching model for accounting the dynamic changes over the whole VA operating range, which would effectively reduce the model mismatches, is part of current work.

Fig. 7. VR’s adhesion properties evaluated under EMPC. On top the generated force F_{VA} and the reference force F_{ref} responses are presented, followed by the control effort response T and last presented is the roll angle ϕ response.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

In this article, the design and evaluation of an EMPC to regulate the adhesion level of a climbing VR has been presented. The controller has been designed for a single model of the system that has been identified by an ARMAX identification at a determined operation point that covers a large bandwidth of the system’s operation region. The controller has been tuned and calculated offline, which minimizes the computation complexity of solving an online optimization problem at every iteration. The validity of the controller was supported by experimental results, where it has been indicated that close to the operating region the proposed scheme performed successfully in accurately controlling the adhesion, while away from the region the controller is diverging, thus introducing the need for a switching modeling and control approach. Future work will include comparative studies between different types of controllers and identification techniques to further improve the control of the overall VR system, while model-based switching EMPC schemes are currently being investigated.

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